

HEALTH IMPACTS OF AIRCRAFT NOISE EXPOSURE

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ABSTRACT:

Aircraft noise is well known as an environmental stressor negatively impacting human health. Recently, systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the scientific evidence (until 2014/2015) regarding the health impact of environmental noise were carried out in order to inform the latest WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region. Within the frame of the EU Horizon 2020 funded research project Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches (ANIMA), the most recent evidence of health implications of aircraft noise was reviewed. The WHO findings were updated by recent studies published between 2014 and 2018, in order to identify priorities for aircraft noise management.

Key findings are that aircraft noise leads to short-term physical and psychological responses that, in the long run, might have implications for physical and mental long-term health. In particular, both the ANIMA and WHO reviews identified evidence of noise annoyance, sleep disturbance, impairment of children's reading comprehension, and ischemic heart diseases being associated with aircraft noise exposure. Furthermore, recent studies show associations between aircraft noise exposure and mental health, especially concerning the risk of depression. There is evidence that aircraft noise annoyance and sleep disturbances at least partly mediate the impact of aircraft noise exposure on long-term health effects.

This review concludes that in order to optimise efforts to mitigate these health risks, airports and other stakeholders should focus on annoyance outcomes in addition to conventional attempts to reduce noise exposure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The EU Horizon 2020 funded research project Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches (ANIMA) investigates novel approaches to improve the quality of life for residents near airports while promoting a compatible development of noise mitigation management.

According to EUROSTAT, health is one of the major indicators for quality of life besides other aspects such as material living conditions, education, economic safety, governance and basic rights [1]. Aircraft noise is well known as an environmental stressor negatively impacting human health. In order to be able to tackle and (re)act to the problem of harmful effects of environmental conditions such as noise exposure, it is essential to understand the underlying mechanisms.

According to the noise-health model by [2], there are two pathways describing the development of detrimental effects of noise on health: On the one hand, noise activates the central nervous system via the direct unconscious pathway [3]. On the other hand, noise provokes disturbance, cognitive and emotional responses via the indirect conscious pathway, summarised in the annoyance reaction. Both pathways can initiate acute physiological stress reactions in the nervous and endocrine (hormonal) system, which in turn can determine changes in other physiological functions such as blood pressure. Acute stress reactions enable the human body to cope with demanding and stressful events. Underlying neuroendocrine and neural activations affecting the metabolic state of the organism might contribute to prolonged stress reactions. Long-term exposure to noise is assumed to affect the effectiveness of the stress-system and in turn negatively affect the cardiovascular system and metabolism.

Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: systematic reviews for an update

In preparation for an update of the Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region [4] systematic reviews were performed to summarize and grade the scientific literature of recent years on the impact of noise on different health outcomes. WHO differentiates health outcomes in crucial and important endpoints [4]. Investigated health outcomes are cardiovascular diseases, annoyance, sleep disturbance, cognitive impairment, quality of life, mental health and well-being, hearing impairment and tinnitus, adverse birth outcomes as well as metabolic diseases.

The systematic reviews for the WHO on impacts of noise on various health outcomes found positive associations between aircraft noise and ischemic heart disease [5], annoyance [6], reading and oral comprehension [7] and sleep disturbance [8]. Less evidence for associations with environmental noise was observed for the other outcomes: adverse birth outcomes [9]; other cardiovascular disease (CVD) and metabolic effects [5]; quality of life, wellbeing and mental health [10], permanent hearing loss and tinnitus [11].

In order to identify gaps as well as priorities for aircraft noise management and to derive the most recent information on key outcomes, supplemental reviews were carried out within the ANIMA project [12]. The focus was on health outcomes except for annoyance, which is comprehensively addressed in another subtask of the ANIMA project [13].

2. PROCEDURE

The current state of research since the WHO reviews has been reviewed to update the evidence on the influence of transportation noise on human health outcomes. Within the ANIMA project, the current state of research to 2019 has been reviewed. For CVD an additional literature screening was implemented in 2019.

Scientific literature databases including PubMed/MEDLINE, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), Scopus (including Embase), EBSCO, and Web of Science, were searched for original studies. Selected search terms were “environmental noise OR transportation noise OR aviation noise OR aircraft noise” in combination with search terms covering the associated types of investigated health outcomes.

The following inclusion criteria were applied:

- 1) Noise exposure measures were implemented with noise measurement or noise mapping;
- 2) Noise source is aviation noise or noise from airports, no combined traffic noise exposure;

- 3) Health outcomes were cardiovascular risk factors/cardiovascular diseases or adverse effects of metabolic system or sleep architecture/sleep disturbance/sleep quality or cognition/cognitive impairment or mental health/quality of life/well-being;
- 4) Relationship between health outcomes and aircraft noise exposure is analysed;
- 5) Studies were published after the deadline of the previous systematic reviews commissioned by the WHO, i.e. mostly published after 2014; studies related to annoyance as mediator were screened also before 2014.

The following noise impact studies are included in the current review: DEBATS [14], HYENA [15], NORAH [16] [17] [18] [19] [20] [21] [22], SAPALDIA [23] [24], SiRENE [25] [26], SDPP cohort [27] [28], and the CEANS cohort [29].

3. RESULTS

In this publication, the focus lies on the presentation of findings on the relationship between aircraft noise and cardiovascular disease, sleep measures, mental health related outcomes, and cognitive impairment. Studies examining the relationship between health outcomes and noise annoyance due to aircraft noise were also reviewed. There are no new original studies investigating the relationship between aircraft noise exposure and adverse birth outcomes and hearing impairment and tinnitus. Results are presented separately for each group of health outcomes.

3.1. Cardiovascular disease

For simplification of illustration, the results for different kinds of cardiovascular disease are grouped: hypertension (hypertensive disease), ischemic heart disease (IHD) including myocardial infarction, the risk of stroke and adverse effects of the metabolic system.

In the systematic review on cardiovascular diseases and adverse metabolic effects for the WHO [5], no significant associations between aircraft noise and increased risk for incident or prevalent hypertension as well as stroke were found; only the incidence of IHD appeared to be significantly associated.

Seven studies investigated the effect of aircraft noise on hypertension; four of them showed aircraft noise to be positively associated with prevalence [14] [15] and incidence of hypertension [15] [28]. Three studies found no significant associations with hypertension [16] [17] [30]. One study observed increased risk for hypertensive heart disease in people exposed to aircraft noise levels between 55 – 59 decibels (dB) [18].

Further, six studies investigated ischemic heart disease (IHD) including myocardial infarction. IHD mortality was found to be associated with aircraft noise [31] while increased risk for incident IHD was observed to be associated with aircraft noise only in women [29]. Four studies observed an association between the exposure to aircraft noise and myocardial infarction mortality [25] [26] [31] [32]. Only one of the reviewed studies found no association between aircraft noise and myocardial infarction [15].

In three studies investigating the impact of aircraft noise on stroke morbidity, no significant increase was found associated with noise measures [15], [29] [33]; only exposure levels of $L_{Aeq,24h} < 40$ dB and at least six events with $L_{Amax} > 50$ dB were associated with elevated risk for stroke [33]. In studies evaluating the effect of aircraft noise on stroke mortality, two studies did not find associations between aircraft noise exposure and increased risks [31] [25] while an association with elevated noise levels was observed in another study [29].

3.2. Adverse metabolic health effects

The WHO review on adverse metabolic health effects observed no association between exposure to aircraft noise and diabetes type II, but found indications for an association with obesity [5].

In recent years, three studies were published on the effect of aircraft noise exposure on adverse metabolic health effects, i.e. obesity or overweight and diabetes type II. Two studies investigated the association between aircraft noise and obesity or overweight; indicating mixed results. While [27] found between aircraft noise exposure and obesity and overweight [34] observed no significant association. For diabetes type II, one study by [23] showed a significant association with aircraft noise.

3.3. Cognition

The WHO review by [7] observed negative implications of aircraft noise for memory functions, attention reading and oral comprehension.

In this review, only one new study was found examining the impact of aircraft noise on children's cognition, showing exposure to aircraft noise to be significantly associated with reading, wellbeing and annoyance [20]. A delay in reading and oral comprehension was identified to be associated with an increase in aircraft noise.

3.4. Sleep

The latest WHO review focussing on the effect of environmental noise on sleep deduces that aircraft noise, among other transportation noise sources, negatively influences - physiologically and psychologically measured - sleep [8].

A total of 13 studies was identified in the current review examining the effect of aircraft noise exposure on sleep as assessed in surveys such as sleep disturbances and sleep quality (self-reported measures) as well as the effect on physiological measures of sleep (via polysomnography and actimetry). Four studies used physiological measures to assess the effect of aircraft noise exposure on sleep and found mixed results. Two studies conducted by DLR (German Aerospace Centre) investigated the effect of noise on sleep using polysomnography. [35] found an association between the night flight ban at Frankfurt airport and a decreased number of awakenings per night. [36] compared the number of awakenings per night of participants exposed to aircraft noise with participants in a control group; showing no difference in number of awakenings between the groups. [37] measured participants' motility during sleep as an indicator for their sleep quality. Participants exposed to higher sound pressure levels displayed more body movements.

Regarding self-reported sleep outcomes, the 12 identified studies used different variables and indicators to assess the impact of aircraft noise exposure on sleep quality or sleep disturbances, which hampers a direct comparison between studies. Five studies assessed sleep disturbances caused by aircraft noise [38] [35] [39] [40] [22]. Seven other studies assessed sleep quality, sleep insufficiency, insomnia, and tiredness [41] [36] [42] [37] [43] [44] [45]. Although the measures of sleep differed greatly between these studies, the majority of studies found an effect of aircraft noise on self-reported sleep measures, i.e. participants reporting a poorer quality of sleep, more sleep disturbances as well as tiredness due to nocturnal aircraft noise.

3.5. Quality of life, wellbeing and mental health

For the WHO, [10] reviewed studies on the relationship between aircraft noise exposure and quality of life (QoL), wellbeing and mental health finding inconsistent results. Due to the small number of studies, it was argued that it is not possible to interpret the results.

In the updated review, seven studies were included examining the impact of aircraft noise exposure on self-reported quality of life and wellbeing [46] [21] [47] [48], self-reported depression, anxiety or (other) psychological symptoms [43] [49], and interview measures of diagnosed unipolar depression [19].

Two studies assessed short-term measures of wellbeing using an experience sampling method linking psychological data with noise contour data; showing higher levels of aircraft noise exposure to be negatively associated with wellbeing [47] [48]. Two sub-studies from the NORAH study

sleep

investigated long-term quality of life in children [46] and adults [21]; both indicating that higher levels of aircraft noise are linked to poorer mental health-related quality of life, which covers the concepts of psychological distress and psychological wellbeing in the subdomain mental-health related quality of life in the health survey questionnaire [50].

Two studies examined self-reported depression and psychological symptoms. Both studies observed no association between aircraft noise levels and depression scores [43] or psychological distress, respectively [49].

Manifest diagnosed depressions were investigated in one study by [19] using health insurance data of residents in the vicinity of Frankfurt Airport. Results indicate a significant relationship between aircraft noise exposure and diagnosed unipolar depression in an inverted u-shape with a peak of risk increase at 50 – 55 dB.

In line with the WHO review, there are inconsistent findings. However, studies indicate aircraft noise exposure to have an impact on quality of life measures as well as on diagnosed depressions.

3.6. Link between annoyance and health outcomes

The WHO did not commission a review on the relationship between annoyance due to aircraft noise and other health outcomes, but they highlight annoyance as a potential mediator of other long-term health impacts [51].

We reviewed articles on this topic to condense findings on the potential relationship and to shed light on this issue.

Studies were found investigating the relationship between noise annoyance caused by aircrafts and cardiovascular diseases [52] [3] [53], sleep [54] [55], quality of life and mental-health related measures [21] [49], and physical activity [24]. Studies examining the relationship between annoyance and health outcomes without underlying noise data are not reported here.

For hypertension, two studies found a positive association between noise annoyance and hypertension; one indicated that the relative risk for hypertension among subjects reporting annoyance was significantly higher than in those not reporting annoyance [52]. The second study showed that only in people with higher annoyance noise levels had a stronger effect on the risk of hypertension [3]. In a cross-sectional study [53] observed no significant association between blood pressure levels and aircraft noise annoyance. Measures differed substantially and, as all of the studies are cross-sectional, the evidence is not sufficient to draw consistent general conclusions.

For sleep measures, two studies investigated the link between annoyance and sleep quality [54] and

disturbance [55]; results of both studies – although differing in measures - indicate a possible association of self-reported sleep measures and noise annoyance.

Two studies were identified focussing mental health and wellbeing related measures. One longitudinal study observed the relationship between aircraft noise annoyance and mental-health related quality of life [21] and one cross-sectional study examined the relationship between aircraft noise annoyance and psychological distress [49]. [21] found a negative association between mental-health related quality of life and annoyance. Analysing the causal pathway revealed annoyance to mediate the effect of noise levels on future mental health-related QoL. Also, a reciprocal association between annoyance and mental health-related QoL was observed. Additionally, mental-health related QoL seemed to negatively influence future annoyance ratings. [49] observed no association between noise exposure and psychological distress, however, psychological distress was linked to aircraft noise annoyance with a strong increase in distress for people being extremely annoyed.

In another longitudinal study, [24] showed that transportation noise annoyance is negatively associated with physical activity; a decrease in moderate physical activity was seen to be a result of a long-time noise annoyance (10 year follow-up).

Results indicate that, to a certain extent, individual appraisals of noise contribute more to the effect on health outcomes than noise levels themselves. Some studies point out that noise annoyance might serve as a mediator between noise exposure and health outcomes. Long-term studies are needed in order to further investigate the causal relationship between annoyance and health outcomes.

More complex models on how health outcomes are affected by noise, noise annoyance and its underlying factors also need further study.

4. DISCUSSION

The systematic reviews for the WHO on impacts of noise on various health outcomes observed positive associations between aircraft noise and ischemic heart disease [5], annoyance [6], reading and oral comprehension [7] and sleep disturbance [8]. For the other outcomes, less evidence was found [5] [9] [10] [11].

The review on noise and health carried out within the ANIMA project examined studies published since the deadline of the WHO review (for most outcomes since 2014). The examination draws a similar picture of inconsistent outcomes; generally

pointing to positive statistical associations with the main health impacts identified by the WHO and summarised in [12]. Furthermore, recent studies not included in the WHO reviews show associations between aircraft noise exposure and mental health, in particular the risk of depression [19].

The WHO reviews imply annoyance and sleep disturbances to be regarded as potential mediators of other long-term health impacts [51]. Our review supports the assumption due to the observation that aircraft noise annoyance and sleep disturbances at least partly mediate the impact of aircraft noise exposure on long-term health effects (e.g. [21] [49]).

Key findings are that aircraft noise leads to short-term physical and psychological responses that, in the longer run, might have implications for physical and mental long-term health. Thus, it can be hypothesised that reducing annoyance and/or sleep disturbance will have a beneficial impact, i.e. decreasing the occurrence of other health outcomes.

5. CONCLUSION

This review concludes that, in order to optimise efforts to mitigate health risks, airports and other aviation-affiliated stakeholders should focus on better understanding annoyance outcomes in addition to conventional attempts to reduce noise exposure. Based on the work done in the ANIMA project we suggest that in order to reduce the detrimental effects of aviation noise on human health, the reduction of annoyance and sleep disturbance should be addressed. For noise mitigation strategies, it is recommended that a more comprehensive approach in the design and the evaluation of noise interventions is adopted. Further, research has found several non-acoustical factors to contribute to noise annoyance (e.g. fairness, trust in authorities, lifestyle factors) that should be taken into account (see [56] for further information).

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